

EFFECTS OF BREWING TECHNIQUE AND PARTICLES SIZE OF GROUND RICE ON A SENSORY PROFILING OF BREWED SAKE BEER

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Abstract: The effect of brewing techniques and particle size of malted rice on the sensory profile of brewed sake beer was investigated. Rice grains were purchased, analysed (grain analysis) and malted. The malts were divided into four equal parts and labelled A, B, C and D. Sample A was finely milled, Sample B was coarsely milled, Sample C was roughly milled while sample D was rough coarsely milled followed by malt analysis. Infusion mashing technique with the aid of exogenous enzymes (α -amylase, β -amylase, β -glucanase and proteinase) were used to obtain worts of varying concentrations. The worts obtained were analyzed, boiled with hops for 1¹/₂ hour and pitched with yeast strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* to commence primary fermentation for 7 days followed by secondary fermentation for 14 days. The resulting beer were analysed for their physicochemical properties. The results of wort analysis showed original gravity, sugar level, pH, flow rate, and viscosity of 1.027⁰ ρ , 6.82⁰Brix, 5.49, 18.50 sec and 1.04cp for sample produced from finely milled grist. Sample produced from coarsely milled grist showed original gravity, sugar level, pH, flow rate, and viscosity of 1.031⁰ ρ , 7.8⁰Brix, 5.58, 18.45 sec and 1.04cp. Sample produced from roughly milled grist showed original gravity, sugar level, pH, flow rate, and viscosity of 1.031⁰ ρ , 7.8⁰Brix, 5.62, 18.68 sec and 1.05cp. Sample produced from roughly milled grist showed original gravity, sugar level, pH, flow rate, and viscosity of 1.028⁰ ρ , 7.06⁰Brix, 5.57, 18.48 sec and 1.04cp. The specific gravity of the beer samples ranged from 1.001 to 1.002⁰ ρ , sugar (0.26–0.52⁰Brix) and alcohol (2.35–2.87)%v/v. There was no significant difference regarding the sensory properties (colour, taste, mouth feel and general acceptability) of the sake beer produced from finely milled, coarsely milled, roughly milled and roughly coarsely milled particle sizes. The result of this investigation revealed that for the malted rice studied, the proportion of the particle with that the best brewing result in terms of extract content, filtration, fermentability and sensory profile, are malts that are coarsely and roughly milled.

Keyword: Brewing, particle size, rice, sake beer

Introduction

Despite the fact that beer production has been around for centuries and its technology is well established, there are still a lot of activities that may be accomplished in a scientific and useful manner (Wunderlich and Back, 2009). Whilst remaining largely a traditional process, the brewing process has over the last century seen

significant advancements in its scientific knowledge and technology (Krebs *et al.*, 2019). Numerous mechanical, biochemical, microbiological, and genetic innovations are used in the malting and brewing sector today. Newer concepts such as the continuous bioreactor with immobilised yeast can decrease maturation times from several weeks to a matter of hours (Dufour *et al.*, 2007; Ofeodu *et al.*, 2021).

Grain malt is one of the four necessary ingredients for making beer, along with water, yeast, and hop. With a dry matter percentage of 51–77%, starch is the most significant component of grain kernels. During the mashing process, starch is transformed into fermentable sugars (Malomo *et al.*, 2011; Zvidzai *et al.*, 2014).

The process of making wort is the initial step in making beer. However, in order to produce wort, it is necessary to grind appropriate (usually barley) malt to get the desired fineness first (Pereira de Moura and Rocha Dos Santos, 2018). Grinding is followed by further processing steps, which include in particular: mashing of malt grist into the water, mashing, wort drawing-off, wort boiling and wort cooling. Cereal grains are malted before their use in the brewing process. The steps involved in malting are steeping, germination, and kilning (Gupta *et al.*, 2010).

Grain starch has a bimodal granule size distribution (Smejtkova *et al.*, 2016). It consists of large, lenticular A-type granules and small spherical B-type granules with respective diameters of 10–35 μm and 2–7 μm (Mousia *et al.*, 2004). According to reports, the tiny starch granules account for 6–30% of barley's overall starch mass. On a number percentage basis, the small starch granules are much more abundant than the large starch granules, with reported quantities ranging between 65 and 97% (de Moura and Dos Santos, 2018).

For the necessary disclosure of extractive substances, contained in the malted grain and accelerating their dissolution, it is necessary to crush the grain (Evans *et al.*, 2014). Two basic components, each of which comprises malted grain, are the husks and endosperm. Husks have a major impact to speed and quality of lautering/filtration (Kuhbeck *et al.*, 2007). The endosperm is composed mainly of starch, carbohydrates and proteins (Martinez *et al.*, 2017). Suitably grinded grain and thus disclosed endosperm enables the desired enzymatic and physical-chemical reactions in the production of the wort (Kamburi and Xhangolli, 2016).

However, the extraction of these soluble components is not the sole objective, consideration must also be given to the rate of wort separation. Malt must therefore constantly be ground as finely as possible to extract the sugars efficiently while preserving enough husk fragments to allow for proper wort separation (Natoniewsky *et al.*, 2018). The grist particle size distribution (PSD) that gives such balance will depend on the type of wort separation system employed. Mash tuns require coarse grists while mash filters and high pressure mash filters can tolerate much finer grists (Schnitzenbaumer *et al.*, 2012). Thus effective milling of malt in the brewery is of crucial importance with regard to the yield of extract and the ease of wort separation (Nehra *et al.*, 2024).

Lautering/filtration is also quite crucial technological step in the production of beer, because it leads to separating of the wort (extract solution) from the malt residue (solid, saccharified mash, spent grain) (Li *et al.*, 2023). Traditional brewing technologies use for lautering is called filtration vat. An alternative to the filtration vat is so called mash filter or lauter tun, but this device can be found in breweries in much lesser extent than filtration vat.

The filtration vat is the most widely used brewing equipment in the Czech Republic, which is renowned for producing high-quality beers that are sought-after on the global market. To fulfil the function of filtration vat properly it is necessary to have the least damaged grist and most thoroughly grinded husks. Other key requirements for malt grist are high proportion of fine semolina (fine grist) and conversely a small proportion of coarse semolina (coarse grist) (Mousia *et al.*, 2004).

The production of malt grist for filtration vat with desired composition malt mills (roller mills) are usually used which contain two, four or six milling rollers (de Moura and Dos Santos, 2018). Conversely, for mash filter hammer mill or a dispersant is usually preferred, as grist should have, on the contrary, well-milled husk for this filter (Evans *et al.*, 2014).

Beers' sensory qualities have a big impact on whether or not customers like them. This has led to a noticeable increase in the quantity of papers and sensory research about beer that have been published in recent years. Grain and malt's proportion of large and small starch granules is frequently overlooked, which undervalues their significance in the processes that use them. Although the importance of milling and particle size is widely acknowledged by the Brewing Industry, there have been comparatively few papers published in this field. Hence, this study was carried out.

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of brewing techniques and particle size of malted rice on the sensory profile of brewed sake beer. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. To determine the grain and malt properties of the rice grain used.
- ii. To mill the malts into various particle sizes
- iii. To determine the physicochemical properties of worts produced
- iv. To determine the physicochemical properties of the sake beer produced
- v. To determine the organoleptic properties of the sake beer produced

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of Materials

The four basic raw materials used for these research were water, malts (rice), hops and yeast. The rice used for this study was purchased from Ugbawka in Nkanu-East LGA of Enugu State. The reagents, equipment, enzymes, yeasts and hops used for this research were supplied by the Laboratory section of the Department of Applied Microbiology and Brewing in Enugu State University of Science and Technology.

Analytical Methods

The methods of analysis employed in the evaluation of grains, malt, wort and beer were based on the recommended methods of analysis of the Institute of Brewing (IOB), American Society of Brewing Chemists (ASBC) and Laboratory Methods in Malting (Agu, 2006)

Methods Used

The methods used in this work were according to that of Institute of Brewing (IOB), America Society of Brewing Chemists (ASBC) and European Brewing Convention (EBC) methods.

Grain Analysis

The red and white sorghum grains were analysed for their germinative energy, germinative capacity, moisture content and thousand corn weight using the Institute of Brewing (IOB) method of analysis.

Malting process

The process of malting involved first selecting the grain, then steeping it for 40 hours (changing the steep liquor every 6 hours and letting the grains air-rest for 2 hours), casting it for 24 hours (draining the water and heaping it on a jute bag), germination (spreading the grains evenly on the jute bag for even aeration and germination) for 3 days, and kilning (drying the malt to lower its moisture content). The rootlets were extracted using friction (abrasion) following kilning.

Malt Analysis

The malted grains were analysed for hot water extract, cold water extract and diastatic power.

Milling Process

The malts were coarsely milled in the form that ensures that the husks are substantially left intact in order to aid filtration after mashing.

Mashing

The rice malt grist (50g of each sample) were weighed into 4 different 500ml conical flask labelled A, B, C and D. A total of 360ml of water was added into each of the conical flask containing the grists. Two milliliters (2ml) of α -amylase, β -amylase, α -1,6 amyloglucosidase, proteinase and β -glucanase were added into each of the conical flask containing the samples and shake properly.

The labelled conical flask containing the samples were covered with aluminium foil and placed in a water bath where the temperature was raised to 35⁰C and maintained for 30mins. The temperature was raised again to 45⁰C and maintained for 30mins for Beta-glucanase activities. The temperature was raised again to 50⁰C and maintained for 30⁰C for proteolysis. The temperature was further raised to 63⁰C and maintained for 1 hour for Beta-amylase activities.

The temperature was then increased to 72⁰C and held there for 30 minutes. These temperatures activate alpha-amylase to act on work converting starch to glucose. One (1) drop of iodine solution was added to 2ml of the mash in a test tube to check for saccharification. After a complete saccharification, which was got through yellowish colour, the worts were vigorously boiled to boiling point for extra 10mins to mash off. The sample (mash) was allowed to cool and filtered using filter cloth to obtain a clear solution known as worts.

Wort Analysis

The parameters determined were original gravity (O.G) ($^{\circ}\rho$), sugar ($^{\circ}\text{Brix}$), pH, flow rate (sec), viscosity (cp), temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and reducing sugar (glucose and maltose). This was done using the method of the Methods of Analysis of the Institute of Brewing.

Wort Boiling

This was carried out before fermentation to sterilize the worts, inactivate the enzymes and extract the hop constituent. The worts were poured into 500ml conical flasks and arranged in water bath, hops (pellets) were added and boiled for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.

Wort cooling and filtration

The hopped boiled worts were cooled to room temperature using heat exchanger technique by placing the conical flasks in a big basin containing cold water. The separation of hop debris and the coagulant protein (trub) from the wort was done with the help of sterile muslin cloth and filter.

Wort Fermentation

The wort was now prepared for yeast fermentation after cooling and aerating. Strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was employed for the fermentation process. The yeast was first reconstituted by mixing 20g of yeast, 10g of glucose with water in a container. It was shake vigorously for 10mins and checked for pressure which signified that the yeast was back to life. Ten (10ml) of the yeast inoculum was added to the worts (pitching) and the container was stocked with cotton wool. The primary fermentation took 7days at 25°C . At the end, the yeasts were skimmed off and the product filtered to obtain green beer which was further allowed for 7days for secondary fermentation at 10°C . After the secondary fermentation, the beer was filtered with filter paper to obtain a bright clear beer.

Beer Analysis

After fermentation, the pH, gravity and percentage alcohol were determined after filtration.

Organoleptic Analysis

Organoleptic test was carried out on the beer produced. A group of ten panellists tested the products and recorded their inferences and insights about the product. The evaluation varied from “dislike extremely” to “liked extremely” for parameters (colour, taste, mouth feel and general acceptability). The judgements were further analysed statistically.

Data Analysis

Analysis off variance (ANOVA) were used to evaluate the parameters. The results of the analysis were tested at $P\leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Worts of varying properties and concentrations were obtained from Ugbawka rice by infusion mashing system. The results of grain analysis showed germinative energy of 98%, germinative capacity of 96%, moisture content

of 8.3% and thousand corn weight of 25g for the Ugbawka rice variety (Table 1). Table 2 showed results of malt analysis. The physicochemical properties of the worts were determined and recorded in Table 3. The highest content of the original gravity which is a measure of dissolved extract was in the mash produced from coarsely and roughly milled malts at approximately 1.031^op (7.8 °Brix). The physicochemical properties of the beer samples after three days, primary and secondary fermentation were recorded in Tables 4, 5 and 6, respectively. Table 7 showed result of sensory evaluation of the beer samples.

Table 1: Grain Analysis

Parameters tested	Ugbawka Rice
Germinative Energy (%)	98
Germinative Capacity (%)	96
Moisture content (%)	8.3
Thousand corn weight (g)	25

Table 2: Malt Analysis

Samples	Hot Water Extract (%/kg)	Cold Water Extract (%)	Diastatic power (°L)
A	267	25.2	26.3
B	278	25	26.16
C	269	24.91	26.04
D	276	24.7	25.96

Key: A = finely milled sample, B = coarsely milled sample, C = roughly milled sample, D = rough coarsely milled sample

Table 3: Wort Analysis

Samples	O.G (°p)	Sugar level (°Brix)	pH	Temp (°C)	Flow rate (Sec)	Viscosity (cp)	Reducing sugars (mg/l)	Glucose	Maltose
A	1.027	6.82	5.49	25	18.50	1.04	54.73	88.80	
B	1.031	7.8	5.58	25	18.45	1.04	50.21	81.17	
C	1.031	7.8	5.62	25	18.68	1.05	50.21	81.17	
D	1.028	7.06	5.57	25	18.48	1.04	54.73	88.80	

Table 4: Physicochemical Properties of the Liquor after 3 days of Fermentation

Samples	Specific Gravity (°ρ)	Sugar level (°Brix)	Temp. (°C)	pH	% Alcohol	Apparent Fermentability (%)
A	1.008	2.05	25	4.02	2.45	70.4
B	1.008	2.05	25	4.19	2.97	74.2
C	1.011	2.81	25	4.20	2.58	64.5
D	1.008	2.05	25	4.01	2.58	71.43

Table 5: Physicochemical Properties of the Green Beers after Primary Fermentation

Samples	Specific Gravity (°ρ)	Sugar level (°Brix)	Temp. (°C)	pH	% Alcohol	Apparent Fermentability (%)
A	1.004	1.03	25	3.95	2.97	85.2
D	1.004	1.03	25	4.00	3.48	87.1
C	1.006	1.54	25	4.04	3.23	80.6
B	1.005	1.29	25	3.90	2.97	82.1

Table 5: Physicochemical Properties of the Beers after Secondary Fermentation

Samples	Specific Gravity (°ρ)	Sugar level (°Brix)	Temp. (°C)	pH	% Alcohol	Apparent Fermentability (%)
A	1.001	0.26	25	3.89	3.35	96.3
B	1.001	0.26	25	3.95	3.87	96.8
C	1.002	0.52	25	3.99	3.74	93.5
D	1.002	0.52	25	3.94	2.35	92.9

Table 7: The Sensory Evaluation Table

	Colour	Taste	Mouth Feel	General Acceptability
F – Cal. Values	1.69	1.41	1.46	1.53
F – Tables values	2.866	2.866	2.866	2.866
LSD	0.321	0.519	0.304	0.222

Key:

F- Cal Value = F – calculated value

F-Tabulated = F – Table values.

LSD = Leas Significant Difference

Discussion

Herein, it was shown that brewing techniques and particle size of malted rice are the key factors affecting the physicochemical properties, fermentation performance, and sensory properties of sake beer. Specifically, reducing particle size increases the contact area between rice malt and water, which promotes the release of rice malt constituents such as bioactive substances, starch, and protein, ultimately leading to improved physicochemical properties, fermentation performance, and high extract yield in rice malts. However, this study focused on the effect of particle size on the quality of sake beer, it will be interesting to reveal the impact of rice varieties and origins in the future.

The findings of the study's from the grain and malt analysis indicate that the grains were viable, had a sufficient moisture level, and suitable for malting.

The physicochemical properties of the worts showed variation in the wort properties obtained from grist of different particle sizes. The size of the crushed malt significantly affects the amount of extract in the mash, according to the results of the analysis shown in Table 4.3. The highest content of the original gravity which is a measure of dissolved extract was in the mash produced from coarsely and roughly milled malts at approximately $1.031^{\circ}\rho$ (7.8°Brix). The lowest dissolved extract content concentration was noted in the mash produced from the finely milled sample at approximately $1.027^{\circ}\rho$ (6.82°Brix). This result should be expected since the smaller particle size of the flour proportion is accompanied with greater area for mass transfer and hence greater extraction efficiency in samples B and C. Also, due to high proportion of the coarse particles in the rice malt there is decrease in the mass transfer area resulting in the low extract yield for grist sample D.

The results of the physicochemical properties of the worts as influenced by various particle sizes, during the manufacturing of sake beer shows that the overall physicochemical properties of the worts produced from different particle sizes did not differ significantly. This result is in agreement with the findings of Xolo *et al.* (2024).

The worts were allowed to ferment and analysed after primary and secondary fermentation. The results of beer analysis after fermentation showed the gravity, sugar and pH to reduce and alcohol produced. The specific gravity of the beer samples ranged from 1.001 to $1.002^{\circ}\rho$, sugar ($0.26\text{--}0.52^{\circ}\text{Brix}$) and alcohol ($2.35\text{--}2.87\%$ v/v). This shows how the yeasts are acting on the wort (Lyumugabe *et al.*, 2012). The value of alcohol produced in this studies is similar to those produced by Xolo *et al.* (2024)

There was no significant difference regarding the sensory properties (colour, taste, mouth feel and general acceptability) of the sake beer produced from finely milled, coarsely milled, roughly milled and roughly coarsely milled particle sizes.

Conclusion

The result of this investigation revealed that for the malted rice studied, the proportion of the particle with that the best brewing result in terms of extract content, filtration, fermentability and sensory profile, are malts that are

coarsely and roughly milled. The result of this study showed acceptability of the sake beer produced from rice malt with varying particle sizes such as finely milled, coarsely milled, roughly milled, and roughly coarsely milled for their organoleptic properties based on parameters (color, taste, mouthfeel, or general acceptability) tested. The results showed that wort with a high fermentable sugar content, including maltose and glucose, could be obtained from coarsely and roughly milled rice malts. Notably, crushing significantly affected the extract yield of rice wort, with coarsely and roughly crushed particle sizes yielded superior greater extraction efficiency to the wort, mainly due to the greater area for mass transfer.

From the findings, the following recommendations were made.

- Since Nigeria is blessed with large quantities of rice grains, thus our universities and research institutes should embark on intensive research on the production of good quality beer especially ale that can compete with those produced from barley malt using rice malts.
- The government as a whole should invest on research whose aim is to make our industries self-sustaining in terms of raw-materials availability and technology know-how if we are going to join the league of industrialized nations.
- It would be interesting to investigate further the re-fermenting process so as to produce a sake beer with better characteristics in terms of alcoholic content and carbonation. Beer flavour might also be improved by using different top fermenting yeast or mashing type.
- To optimize the mashing conditions with an increase in starch conversion to reducing sugars, coarse milling is recommended.
- Also, in brewing industries more attention should be given to particle sizes of malts as they significantly contribute to the overall properties of finished beer.

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